

Defensive Publication:

Integrated Thermal Appliance with Electrochemical Energy Storage and Service-Level-Aware Control

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Abstract

This defensive publication discloses integrated thermal appliance designs that combine electrochemical energy storage, electric water heating, and service-level-aware control within a single shippable enclosure or assembly. The disclosed appliances may replace or supplement conventional water heaters—both instantaneous and storage-tank types—while incorporating battery cells, power electronics, a controller, and optionally a water storage volume. The controller modulates hot water service level as a function of stored electrical energy, external source availability, and user preferences, as described in the companion disclosure (DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.19544002](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19544002)). Multiple form factors are disclosed, ranging from tankless wall-mount units to floor-standing tank units, with AC mains input, DC source input, or both. This disclosure is published as prior art to place the described appliance designs, integration methods, and combinations on the public record.

1 Companion Disclosure

This publication complements the companion defensive publication “Energy-Aware Electric Hot Water Systems with Topology-Modeled Control and Service-Level Degradation” (DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.19544002](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19544002)), which discloses the broader control methods, topology models, and system architectures for coordinating electric hot water service

level with available electrical energy. The present disclosure focuses on the **physical integration** of those concepts into self-contained appliance products and dedicated companion modules.

All terminology defined in the companion disclosure applies here. In particular, “service level,” “available-energy state,” “thermal load,” and “topology model” retain the same broad, non-limiting meanings.

2 Field of the Invention

This disclosure relates to integrated domestic or commercial hot water appliances that incorporate electrochemical energy storage within the appliance enclosure or as a directly attached module, together with control logic that modulates hot water service level based on the stored energy state and external source conditions.

3 Terminology and Scope

Unless stated otherwise, the following terms are used broadly and non-limitingly in this publication:

- **Integrated thermal appliance:** A self-contained or directly coupled assembly that includes hot-water heating functionality, electrochemical energy storage, and a controller within one product, one enclosure, or a fixed multi-module appliance package.
- **Electrochemical storage module:** One or

more battery cells, packs, or equivalent electrically rechargeable storage elements, together with any associated BMS, protection, and interface hardware.

- **Service level:** A discrete or continuous operating target for hot-water delivery, including one or more of outlet temperature, temperature rise, flow rate, heating power, availability window, recovery time, or user-priority state.
- **Directly attached module:** A module mechanically and electrically intended to function as part of the appliance at installation time, even if housed in a separate but dedicated companion enclosure.

This disclosure focuses on appliance-level physical integration, packaging, internal power architecture, service interfaces, and installation form factors. General control concepts and topology-model concepts are described in more detail in the companion disclosure.

4 Background

Conventional water heaters—whether instantaneous or tank-based—draw power from an external supply (mains AC, gas, solar thermal, or another upstream source) and typically do not integrate electrochemical energy storage or appliance-local control that modulates service level as a function of stored electrical energy and source conditions. Storage-tank heaters may provide thermal buffering, but they do not by themselves provide the appliance architecture disclosed here.

Separately, residential battery storage systems exist as standalone cabinets that supply the household AC bus. Connecting a conventional water heater to such a system requires the user to assemble, wire, commission, and maintain multiple separate devices from different manufacturers, with no integrated control of service level versus stored energy.

The present disclosure addresses that integration gap by packaging battery storage, water heating, and service-level-aware control into a single appliance that can be installed, commissioned, and maintained as one unit.

5 Appliance Architecture

5.1 Core Subsystems

The integrated appliance may comprise some or all of the following subsystems within a single enclosure or directly coupled assembly:

1. **Electrochemical storage module:** One or more battery cells or packs (e.g., LiFePO_4 or equivalent chemistry), with an integrated or closely coupled battery management system (BMS) providing cell balancing, protection, and state reporting. The module may be removable, field replaceable, or permanently installed.
2. **Heating subsystem:** One or more of:
 - Resistive heating element(s) for instantaneous (tankless) operation.
 - Resistive heating element(s) immersed in an integrated water storage tank.
 - A combination of both: a storage volume for pre-heating and an instantaneous boost stage.
3. **Water storage volume** (optional): An insulated tank integrated within the appliance enclosure. When present, the tank serves as both a thermal buffer and a hydraulic reservoir. Capacity may range from a small buffer (5–30 L for boost applications) to a full domestic tank (50–300 L).
4. **Power electronics:** One or more of:
 - AC/DC rectifier or charger stage for mains AC input.
 - DC/DC converter for external DC source input (e.g., PV string, external battery, DC bus).
 - DC power stage (PWM, phase-cut, or switched resistor bank) driving the heating element(s) from the internal DC bus.
 - Optional DC/AC inverter stage for supplying AC power to external loads or feeding excess energy back to the household.
5. **Controller:** An embedded computing system implementing the service-level-aware control algorithm described in the companion disclosure. The controller:
 - Monitors battery SoC, cell temperatures, available charge and discharge power.
 - Monitors water temperatures (inlet, outlet, tank stratification if applicable), flow rate, and demand state.
 - Determines the current service level based on stored energy, external source availability,

user preferences, time-of-use schedules, and safety constraints.

- Modulates heating power, target temperature, and optionally flow or mixing accordingly.
6. **Sensors:** Flow sensor, inlet and outlet temperature sensors, tank temperature sensor(s) if applicable, current and voltage sensors for the DC bus and AC input, and optionally water quality or leak detection sensors.
 7. **Communication interface:** One or more external interfaces for integration with a household energy management system, external inverter, smart home platform, or cloud service. Protocols may include Modbus RTU/TCP, CAN bus, REST API, MQTT, Wi-Fi, Ethernet, or equivalent.
 8. **External source input(s):** One or more of:
 - AC mains input (single-phase or three-phase).
 - DC input for direct PV string connection (with integrated MPPT) or external battery/DC bus connection.
 - Both AC and DC inputs simultaneously.

5.2 Internal DC Bus

The appliance operates internally around a DC bus connecting the battery module, power electronics, and heating element(s). This architecture allows the heating element to draw power from the battery without DC/AC/DC conversion losses, regardless of whether the external input is AC or DC. The DC bus voltage is determined by the battery configuration and may be low voltage (e.g., 12–48 V) or high voltage (e.g., 100–400 V).

5.3 Modular Battery Compartment

In one embodiment, the appliance includes a standardized battery compartment or bay accepting field-replaceable battery modules. This allows:

- Initial installation with a chosen battery capacity.
- Capacity upgrade by replacing modules with higher-capacity versions.
- End-of-life battery replacement without replacing the entire appliance.
- Choice of battery chemistry at installation time, provided the module meets the electrical and mechanical interface specification.

6 Form Factors

The disclosure covers multiple form factors, each representing a different integration point on the spectrum from minimal to maximal integration.

6.1 Form Factor A: Tankless Unit

A wall-mounted unit with no integrated water storage, comparable in size and mounting to a conventional instantaneous water heater but including battery cells and power electronics. Water is heated on demand as it flows through. Service level is modulated by the controller based on available stored energy and input conditions.

Representative dimensions are comparable to a conventional Durchlauferhitzer plus the volume occupied by battery cells and power electronics. For a unit with 5 kWh of LiFePO₄ storage at pack-level density of ~0.22 kWh/L, the battery volume is approximately 23 L, adding roughly 30–40 L to the overall enclosure volume after accounting for structure, cooling, and electronics.

6.2 Form Factor B: Tank Unit (Floor or Wall)

A unit integrating a water storage tank (50–300 L), battery module, heating element(s), and controller. Comparable in installation footprint to a conventional electric storage water heater (Boiler) but with added battery capacity and intelligent control.

The tank provides thermal buffering: the controller pre-heats the tank when energy is abundant (high battery SoC, active solar generation, or low-tariff period) and draws from the stored hot water when energy is scarce, reducing or eliminating instantaneous heating demand.

6.3 Form Factor C: Split Appliance

A two-part system consisting of:

- An indoor heater unit (tankless or with small buffer tank) installed at or near the point of use.
- A separate battery and power electronics module installed in a utility area, basement, or outdoor enclosure.

The two parts are connected by a DC cable for power and a communication link for control. This form factor allows the battery module to be placed in a location better suited for weight, ventilation,

or temperature requirements while the heater unit remains compact at the point of use.

6.4 Form Factor D: Add-On Module

A battery and controller module designed to attach to or integrate with an existing conventional water heater. The module intercepts or supplements the power supply to the existing heater and applies service-level-aware control. This form factor enables retrofit without replacing the existing heater.

The module may:

- Intercept the AC supply to the existing heater, limiting power via relay, contactor, or solid-state switch.
- Supply DC power to a supplementary heating element added to the existing tank.
- Control the existing heater’s thermostat set-point via a motorized or electronic thermostat adapter.

7 Control Integration

7.1 Standalone Operation

The appliance may operate fully standalone, using only its internal battery state and AC/DC input availability to determine service level. No external energy management system is required.

7.2 Coordinated Operation

When connected to an external energy management system, household inverter, or building automation system, the appliance may receive external signals such as:

- Available surplus power or recommended charge/discharge schedules.
- Time-of-use tariff information.
- Demand-response signals (e.g., grid operator curtailment requests).
- Occupancy or usage predictions from a smart home system.

The appliance may also expose its state—including battery SoC, water temperature, current service level, and available capacity—to the external system, enabling the appliance to participate as a node in the topology model described in the companion disclosure.

7.3 Multi-Unit Coordination

In installations with multiple integrated appliances (e.g., one per bathroom, or a central unit plus de-central boost units), the appliances may coordinate with each other directly or through a central controller. Coordination may include:

- Shared battery state awareness to avoid simultaneous peak discharge.
- Priority-based service allocation across multiple points of use.
- Cascaded pre-heat and boost arrangements where one unit’s output feeds another’s inlet.

8 Safety Considerations

The integration of electrochemical storage with water heating introduces safety requirements beyond those of conventional water heaters. The disclosed appliance designs include provisions for:

- **Thermal isolation:** Physical and thermal separation between battery cells and hot water paths to prevent battery overheating from the water heating subsystem and to prevent water ingress into the battery compartment.
- **Battery safety:** Cell-level and pack-level protection including over-voltage, under-voltage, over-current, over-temperature, and short-circuit protection via the BMS.
- **Water safety:** Over-temperature cutoff, scalding protection (maximum outlet temperature limit), dry-fire protection, pressure relief, and leak detection.
- **Electrical safety:** Ground-fault detection, isolation monitoring (particularly for DC systems), arc-fault detection, and safe shutdown sequencing.
- **Ventilation:** Provision for battery gas venting in the event of cell failure, with routing that prevents exposure of occupants or water system to vented gases.
- **Serviceability:** Design for safe battery module replacement by a qualified technician, including mechanical interlocks and electrical disconnection verification.

Battery capacity	Volume (approx.)	Weight (approx.)	Showers (approx.)
2 kWh	10 L	15 kg	1–2
5 kWh	23 L	35 kg	3–5
10 kWh	45 L	70 kg	6–10
20 kWh	90 L	140 kg	12–20

Table 1: Illustrative battery sizing at LiFePO_4 pack-level density (~ 0.22 kWh/L, ~ 0.14 kWh/kg). Shower count assumes 8 L/min, 34 K rise, 5 min duration (~ 1.6 kWh per shower). Actual values vary by chemistry, pack design, and usage pattern.

9 Key Physical Parameters

9.1 Battery Sizing Within the Appliance

9.2 Combined Volume Estimate

For a tankless wall-mount unit with 5 kWh battery:

- Battery module: ~ 23 L
- Power electronics and controller: ~ 5 – 10 L
- Heating chamber and hydraulics: ~ 2 – 5 L
- Enclosure overhead: ~ 5 – 10 L
- Total: ~ 35 – 50 L (~ 40 – 60 cm \times ~ 30 – 40 cm \times ~ 25 – 35 cm)

For a tank unit with 10 kWh battery and 150 L tank, the overall volume is dominated by the tank (~ 150 L) plus battery (~ 45 L) and electronics (~ 10 L), resulting in a unit comparable to a conventional 200–250 L storage water heater.

10 Aspects Disclosed as Prior Art

The following aspects are disclosed as prior art, individually and in combination, extending the companion disclosure (DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.19544002](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19544002)):

1. An integrated thermal appliance combining electrochemical energy storage, electric water heating capability, and local service-level-aware control within a single enclosure or directly coupled appliance assembly.
2. Appliance form factors in which that integration is realized as a tankless wall-mount unit, a tank-based unit, a hybrid tank-plus-boost unit, a split unit with dedicated battery module, or a retrofit add-on module intended to convert an existing heater into an integrated appliance system.

3. An internal DC bus architecture inside such an appliance, connecting electrochemical storage to heating element(s) and associated power electronics, including embodiments that avoid unnecessary DC/AC/DC conversion between the internal battery and the heating path.
4. A modular or field-replaceable battery compartment allowing capacity selection at installation, upgrade over the appliance lifetime, chemistry substitution subject to interface compatibility, and end-of-life replacement without replacing the entire appliance.
5. Appliance operation modes in which the integrated unit functions standalone from internal state and local inputs, or coordinates with external energy management systems, inverters, or building automation while remaining a self-contained thermal appliance.
6. Multi-unit arrangements in which multiple integrated appliances coordinate service priority, peak discharge behavior, or staged pre-heat and boost relationships.
7. Dual AC and DC external input capability in an integrated thermal appliance, allowing the appliance to accept mains AC, direct PV DC with integrated MPPT, external battery/DC bus connections, or combinations thereof.
8. Safety and serviceability provisions specific to the co-location of electrochemical storage and water-heating hardware within one appliance product, including thermal isolation, controlled venting, leak detection, safe shutdown, and qualified battery module replacement procedures.

11 Scope Clarifications

To avoid narrowing by example, this disclosure is expressly not limited to:

- any specific battery chemistry, voltage, or capacity,
- any specific heating element type or power level,
- any specific tank volume or absence of tank,
- any specific form factor, mounting method, or enclosure design,
- residential applications only,
- any specific communication protocol or external interface,
- a single controller or a single point of use,
- any specific country, voltage standard, or regulatory framework.

12 Defensive Publication

This disclosure is published as prior art to place the described appliance designs, integration methods, and combinations on the public record and to reduce the risk of later third-party patent claims over the same subject matter, to the extent permitted by applicable patent law. The author does not intend to seek patent protection on the disclosed subject matter and intends that others may implement, manufacture, use, modify, and sell systems practicing it.

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